

Faculty's turnover in private higher learning Institutions: A phenomenal inquiry

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Abstract: Quality of the faculty is one of the most important components of higher education's quality assurance. Turnover among faculty however could undermine the efficiency, productivity and in some occasions, threatens the institution's long term survival. Preliminary interviews with human resource personnel of selected private higher institutions revealed a high turnover rate of 18%. This qualitative phenomenological study explored the reason on why faculty resigns their job. In depth interviews were conducted with faculty members from 5 private universities in Malaysia, using purposive sampling. The NVivo 8 software was used to analyze the data thematically. Seven major themes emerged from the analysis including; employer image, availability of external job opportunities, social media bullying, unfair performance measurement, unfair compensation, work over load and job insecurity. Although some emerging themes could be traced to previous literatures, an emerging theme of social media bullying warrants further scrutiny. The research results could help private universities to strategize how to minimize the high turnover rates while optimizing the levels of faculty retention. Furthermore this research provides some initial insight on the role of social media bullying in turnover literature.

JEL Classifications: J50, J53, J80, M54

Keywords: Turnover, employer image, cyber bullying, procedural justice, distributive justice, job insecurity, workload and perceived job opportunity

Citation: Ramasamy, V., & Abdullah, N. H. (2017). Faculty's turnover in private higher learning Institutions: A phenomenal inquiry. *Business and Economic Horizons*, 13(2), 169-181, <http://dx.doi.org/10.15208/beh.2017.13>

1. Introduction

Higher education plays an important role in developing knowledge capital to development any country as it not only functions as a provider of knowledge, but also as a relevant sector for the nation's growth and societal well-being. Thillaisundaram (2003) suggests higher education's contribution is not only in producing outputs of research (knowledge extension) and teaching (transmission of knowledge) but also has a general community and social service role to play.

Malaysian higher educational institutions are experiencing exponential growth as a result of government development of the education industry (Ahsan, Abudullah, David, & Alam, 2009; Kanji & Malik, 1998; Ministry of Higher Education of Malaysia, 2012; Mohamed, 2006). According to Ministry of Education (MOE), in 1957, Malaysia had just one university but by 2014, the number of higher education institutions had raised to 20 public universities and 36 private universities (MOE, 2012) the increase in education institutions in Malaysia is mainly due to the increasing number of Malaysians searching for tertiary education. It is also compounded by an increase in the number of public and private higher education institutions, an increase in student enrolment, an increase in government spending on higher education especially public institutions, additional government policies in promoting education, and the country's continuous need for human resources (Kanji & Malik, 1998). The number of private universities in the country

is quite significant therefore the extensive higher education plan should be continuously evaluated so that the expansion will undoubtedly be in accordance with the target of the Eleventh Malaysia Plan (2015 to 2020) and the New Economic Model that drives the country towards being a high-income nation by year 2020

In Malaysia, the average annual turnover rate has risen from 12.3% in 2012 to 13.2% in 2013 (Towers Watson, 2013) indicating that employee turnover will continue to be an issue to employers while turnover rate of faculty at private universities is around 18 % as quoted by human resource personnel of some private university. A thorough understanding of why faculty leaves their jobs requires the knowledge of the faculty's perceptions concerning the decision to leave their jobs by the respective faculty.

Although faculty turnover would affect students' learning development in university and yet there is very little research has been done on why they quit their job. Moreover faculty turnover research done so far has been mostly focused on public university (Idris, O' Driscoll & Anderson, 2011; Hassan & Hashim, 2011) and very few attempts have been made on private university.

Therefore, in this research, the researcher contributes by exploring on why faculty leaves their job and by knowing the causes; it provides an opportunity for university administration to address the issues and make appropriate changes to retain the faculty. The researcher summarizes the above by presenting the following research questions for this study why the faculty left the previous education institution?

2. Literature review

Turnover intention

According to Abbasi & Hollman (2000), employee turnover can be categories as: voluntary and involuntary. Voluntary turnover occurs when the employee themselves resign from their job whereas involuntary turnover refers to dismissal of employees by the employer. Lambert (2001) has also described voluntary turnover as a consequence of employees themselves initiating the termination of their employee-organization relationship. Voluntarily exit an organization is also defined as turnover intention (Nazim, 2008).

Theories on turnover - March and Simon Model

One of the earliest and perhaps most influential integrative models of employee turnover was presented by March and Simon (1958). The March & Simon "Decision to Participate" model has two distinct and interrelated components, perceived desirability of movement and perceived ease of movement from the organization. Major factors affecting perceived desirability of movement are job satisfaction and perceived possibility of intra-organizational transfer. Job satisfaction is considered a function of conformity of the job to self-image, predictability of job relationships, and compatibility of job and other roles. Where conformity of job to self-image are considered a function of supervisory practices, amount of reward, participation in job assignment, education, and rate of change of status and/or income (March & Simon, 1958, pp. 93-97).

There are two major factors affecting perceived ease of movement. The first factor is availability of jobs for which the individual is qualified (and willing to accept) in organizations visible to him. While the second one is extra-organizational alternatives which is considered a function of the level of business activity (March & Simon, 1958, pp. 100-101); personal characteristics of participants, including sex, age, social status, tenure

and specialization (March & Simon, 1958, pp. 101-102); and the number of visible organizations.

The March and Simon model is noteworthy as perhaps the first one to attempt a systematic integration of the economic-labor market and individual behavior. A variety of psychological mechanisms were suggested for linking individual turnover behavior with economic, organizational, and demographic variables. This theory relates very much to the study of turnover intention of faculty members in private higher educational sector. The issues such as what kind of dissatisfaction factors that have significant value and influence on the faculty members turnover intention are great interest in the current study

Theories on turnover - Equity theory

Adams' work on equity (Adams, 1965) was one of the first studies in psychology on perceptions of people regarding the allocation of outcomes (Cohen-Charash & Spector, 2001). Equity theory (Adams, 1965) draws from exchange, dissonance, and social comparison theories in making predictions about how individuals manage their relationships with others. The theory claims that individuals in organizations compare the ratios of their own outcomes, normally tangible rewards, to inputs, such as contributions, to the ratios of other organizational referents. The comparisons will lead to adjustment of work behaviors. That is, when the comparisons yield big differences, people will be motivated to change the situation by either modifying their inputs and outcomes, changing their referent other, distorting their perception, or leaving the organization (Mitchell, Holtom, Lee, Sablinski, & Erez, 2001).

Adam (1965) claimed that people do care, whether the outcomes they received are fair or not. Individuals arrive at a sense of equity or fairness through the comparison of ratio inputs (contributions) and outputs (rewards) in reference to others within an organization. When people perceive equity within the workplace, they are satisfied. According to this theory, individuals will adjust their behavior or mental perceptions to change from unpleasant inequitable states to pleasant equitable ones when they perceive fairness (Greenberg, 1990).

Current study also takes into account the proposition of this theory as faculty compare their own outcomes against the inputs they contribute towards the institution and at the same time also compare with other members in the same faculty.

Previous studies on factors affecting turnover intention

Mobley (1982) described employee turnover as "cessation of employment ties", consists of quits, layoffs, and discharges. In general terms it's the cessation of membership in an organization by an individual who received monetary compensation from the organization. First the focus is on cessation, means separation from the organization and not transfer or internal movement within an organization. Secondly the focus is on employees, those who receive monetary compensation from the organization as a condition of membership (Mobley, 1977).

In study of Hassan & Hashim (2011) on the role of organization justice in shaping teaching faculties' attitude (job satisfaction and commitment) and behavioral intention (turnover intention) at four Malaysian public university found that procedural justice was significantly related to job satisfaction and turnover intention was negatively associated with perceived distributive justice.

Furthermore, an individual would increase his job search when he feels a misfit within an organization. This means the person will rigorously search for a new job when he or she is not satisfied with his or her current job and will only leave the organization if they believe that alternative job opportunities exist (Wheeler, Buckley, Halbesleben, Brouer, & Ferris,

2005). According to Kowalski (2008) and Mesch (2009), cyber bullying is a different phenomenon than traditional bullying. Cyber bullying might be more prominent than traditional bullying.

Furthermore cyber bullying is also worse than traditional bullying because it subjects the victim to humiliation from a larger audience, as verbal harassments, pictures, and taunts can be spread throughout a peer group through current communication technology (Mesch, 2009). The impact of bullying is reported to cause poor performance, damaged psychological health, and instill strong desire to leave the job (Einarsen, Hoel, Zapf, & Cooper, 2003; O'Connell, Calvert, & Watson, 2007). While, Bryant, & Buttigieg (2009) suggest that bullying is directly correlated with low job satisfaction, high employee turnover, increased absenteeism, and decreased levels of organizational commitment.

Employer image as a means of attracting new employees and retaining existing employees is gaining popularity, particularly in employment contexts where the unique talents and contribution of an employee's represent a distinctive competitive advantage for the organization (Heilmann, 2010). Branding in higher education gives institutions an identity that locates them in the social world. Branding gives community members the ability to recognize an institution through a logo (trademark). Although branding goes beyond recognition, students and staffs like to see themselves in that institution and to associate themselves with their history of excellence (Pride & Ferrell, 2003). Since competition for the best employees becomes almost as fierce as competition for customers (Berthon et al., 2005), organizations have to differentiate themselves from their competitors and to be seen as attractive employers for prospective applicants and current employees to stay (Lievens & Highhouse, 2003).

In the research of Crews, Wilkinson, Hemby, McCannon, & Wiedmaier (2008), they state, "Teaching online has the reputation of requiring more work than teaching in a traditional classroom" (p. 132). The research illustrates that effective online teaching requires not only considerable faculty preparation before the course begins but also the active involvement of faculty during the course. The barriers to faculty success were attributed to the increased workload due to the time needed to design and deliver the online course and the depth of engagement during the course.

Job insecurity also impact the faculty on various aspect like high anxiety and stress levels, lack of motivation and commitment, general dissatisfaction with working conditions, and distrust towards the organization. It is further confirmed by the study by Jiménez, Milfener, Žižek, & Dunkl (2017) on the relationship among job insecurity, job satisfaction, and the intention to quit on 251 Slovene and 219 Austrian workers, they found that job insecurity is related to higher stress and intention to quit. Although most of the researches that have been carried out in the past have indicated that there is relationship between various organizational and individual variables with employees' turnover intention but there has not been much of them which were done in the Malaysian education sector, especially in private university. Therefore, a research or study in the private university of Malaysia was needed in order to understand the reason for turnover.

This is the gap that the current study is trying to fill. In particular, the phenomenological nature of the current research effort was performed to allow a greater understanding of issues related to turnover from a resigned faculty member's perspective. Only then can administer and those in the educational leadership community have the knowledge required from which to develop and propose effective interventions.

3. Methodology

Tufford & Newman (2012) noted the qualitative research methodology is appropriate when the researcher seeks to understand, discover, and interpret how the participants experienced a phenomenon.

To further enhance the phenomenon, this research has been pursued within a qualitative perspective, based on the use of in depth interviews. Additionally, qualitative research provides a deeper understanding and insight into the realities of the faculty's past experiences from the perspective of faculty themselves. The research aim is to detect main themes on faculty member's reason to leave their respective jobs.

In terms of selecting research sample, the researched used purposeful self-sampling technique. Purposive or judgmental sampling technique enables researcher to use own judgment to select cases that will best enable to answer the research question(s) and to meet the objectives. (Saunders, Lewis, & Thornill, 2009, p. 240). It was necessary in order to find participants who are knowledgeable, are able to provide balanced perspectives, and will contribute to the theoretical framework of the study (DeCuir-Gunby, 2008).

In phenomenon inquiries, purposeful sampling may involve 5 to 25 participants (Creswell, 2005; Denzin & Lincoln, 2005; Patton, 2002). Those selected are considered essential in respect of their experience and issue they encounter prior to quitting their faculty position.

Initially, eight participants were contacted of which five agreed to participate in this research. The faculty is chosen through personal contact and seeks their permission to conduct interviews. Objective of the research were explained before start of the interview process.

The interviews of the participants took place as per researched journal where the participants were interviewed at private room of the faculty member's organization of choice. A quiet and confidential location for the interview as it was necessary to ensure confidentiality, easy access to the participant, comfort for the participant, and cut down on noise and interruptions for the recording (Gill, Stewart, Treasure, & Chadwick, 2008; Jacob & Furgerson, 2012). The quiet and confidential location also allowed the participant to focus on the interview questions (Gill et al., 2008).

Russell et al. (2011) found that the use of appropriate interview protocol, which included interview questions, yielded consistent information and promoted value and reliability. The results of research postulated that member checking allowed the participant to review the information recorded to verify its validity and conveyed the true experiences of the participant (Kisely & Kendall, 2011; Stuckey, 2014; Thomas & Magilvy, 2011). NVivo was a qualitative data analysis (QDA) software package designed for qualitative researchers working with rich text-based information. Grasso, Genest, Yung, & Arnold (2014) and West (2012) found the use of electronic software promoted reliability as it left less room for human error.

The researcher asked identical questions to all the respondents, but the responses were open-ended, which enabled the participants to provide detailed information based on their experience, while at the same time enabling the researcher to pose follow-up questions. The follow-up questions were asked to obtain more clarity and in-depth coverage of responses. By asking faculty on why they resign from their previous jobs, the researcher aimed to unearth several key factors related to turnover identified in the literature review.

No of interviewee depended on data saturation point. In other words, the researcher will continue to collect qualitative data until data saturation is reached, means until the additional data collected provides few, if any, new insights. In this research data reached the saturation point after interviewing 5 participants.

One time face to face interview with 5 participants were conducted, with an average duration per interview of 45 minutes. Interview was recorded and transcribed using word file. The transcribed data were sent to participant for verification purpose. The researcher used several steps for coding purposes. After reviewing the interviews and the researcher's journals several times, the researcher uploaded the transcribed data into the NVivo software for assistance with coding and was subsequently coded. Words or short phrases were assigned codes that best captured the meaning of the participant's expressions. Codes emerged during several readings of the responses and labels were assigned based upon the text and revised accordingly as new data were analyzed (Miles & Hubermann,

1994). The coding process entailed extracting relevant categories, themes and concepts from the data. The aim of content analysis was to identify the most frequent reasons for turnover by faculty.

4. Analysis & results

Table 1 shows demographic information of the five participants who agreed to be interviewed. They are faculty members who have worked more than three years and just (less than one year) resigned from tier 5 private universities.

TABLE 1. DEMOGRAPHIC INFORMATION

PARTICIPANTS	GENDER	AGE	EDUCATION LEVEL
RESPONDENT 1	F	36	MASTER
RESPONDENT 2	M	34	MASTER
RESPONDENT 3	M	45	DOCTORATE
RESPONDENT 4	M	39	MASTER
RESPONDENT 5	F	32	MASTER

TABLE 2. SUMMARY OF FINDINGS

THEMES	RES 1	RES 2	RES 3	RES 4	RES 5
EMPLOYER IMAGE	X	X	X	X	X
EXTERNAL JOB OPPORTUNITIES	X	X	X	X	X
SOCIAL MEDIA BULLYING	X	X	X	X	X
UNFAIR PERFORMANCE MEASUREMENT	X	X	X	X	X
UNFAIR COMPENSATION	X	X	X	X	X
WORK OVERLOAD	X	X			X
JOB INSECURITY	X	X			X

The interview question focused on the experiences of faculty who have resigned from their job due to various reasons. Seven main themes identified form the explanations provided by the interviews as shown in Table 2. The first five themes emerged consistently among all the five respondents while the last two themes were shared by only three respondents.

Theme 1: Employer Image

Employer image as a means of attracting new employees and retaining existing employees is gaining popularity, particularly in employment contexts where the unique talents and contributions of employees represent a distinctive competitive advantage for organizations (Heilmann, 2010)

Universities' image in higher education sector gives an identity that locates them in the social world. It also gives community members the ability to recognize an institution through their logo (trademark). Although universities' image goes beyond recognition, students, staff and faculty like to see themselves in that institution and to associate

themselves with their history of excellence. The attractiveness of an organization is also an important factor in recruiting and retaining employees (Edwards, 2010)

The attractiveness of a universities' image plays an important factor in recruiting and retaining faculty as it provides a sense of pride and belonging to an institution. We observed many respondent like to work with a popular or branded university as they believe by working with reputed university it helps in their career growth as we can see from below comments from respondent 1

... They have what to do task for them and if they want to grow they have more opportunity and then if you work in the university it involves image and you want to move to another university it will be easier for you because you used to work in university.

It is further supported by another respondent # 5, who commented that working in a reputable university helps in personal development. Here is her comment.

... as a law lecturer it always, prestigious for us to teach in the law degree programme, teaching the law student, and off cause in terms of personal development, with regards to law., it's always, it personally develop our knowledge.

Furthermore working in reputable university also increase faculty self-satisfaction as they believe it gives them some sort of recognition or achievement in their career building. Here is the comment from respondent # 4

... work with more.... how to say...., top corporation at one point of their live because it would mean that, ok I have gained the experience, I have worked in this companies., before in this industry, so to certain extent, at certain point of life, okay a kind of recognition can gain from their peers... you know...., all like that, working in reputable company is and all that, to certain extent, ... yeah..

Therefore faculty prefers to work in an established university as this will enhance their career progression and personal development.

Theme 2: External job opportunities

As the country is planning to become an education hub, there are lots of local universities which are expanding their operation all over the country while foreign universities are also opening their branch campuses over here. Hence create more job opportunity for current faculty especially for those working in private universities. When employees perceive more alternative job opportunities and receive offers from other employers they make a comparison of cost and benefit between current and alternative jobs, if the benefits of the jobs appear to be greater than the costs, employees may quit their jobs. (Mobley, 1977; Price, 2001).

Furthermore, an individual would increase his job search when he feels a misfit within an organization. This means the person will rigorously search for a new job when he or she is not satisfied with his or her current job and will only leave the organization if they believe that alternative job opportunities exist (Wheeler et al. 2005).

If faculty has experience and knowledge it is easier to find job outside the institution. Here is the comment from respondent # 4;

... there is lot of opportunity for teaching professional in Malaysia at least for next 5 or 10 years, as of now, I feel., yes there is good opportunity around ..., mostly in private university, public university are ..., I don't know per say, but private university, yes I feel there are lot of opportunities,

As we become an education hub, there are lot universities offering various programmes which attract lot of student to their programme which indirectly creates an opportunity for faculty. Here is respondent # 5 comment;

... the market is quite good, have very good enrolment, have quite number of intuitions, is providing this programme, so in think in that sense, I don't see any lack, means students are lacking in this profession, in this area, we have quite number of student , we have demand for the programme...

Therefore as country becomes an education hub, it creates lot of job opportunity for faculty.

... it's all experience and publication ...when you have a suitable experience... the other organization needed ... definitely they recruit you..., you have the qualification ... Phd qualification ... that's the main requirement in an education organization, so definitely the external university need you ...

Theme 3: Social media bullying

Bullying through social media is a new phenomenon. The increasing use of computers and cell phones has allowed youth to use these venues for cyber bullying (Marczak & Coyne, 2010). It is also worse than traditional bullying because it subjects the victim to humiliation from a larger audience, as verbal harassments, pictures, and taunts can be spread through social media, like Facebook, Twitter or WhatsApp application. This creates pressure and embarrassment to the faculty hence forcing them to leave an institution. Here is comment from respondent # 1;

.... the student took photo of me and post it in Facebook, saying that, the teacher playing in the phone... you see, they post all kind of things, I feel like stress, you see, that is bad impression of lecturer, and when the people see the Facebook, I mean the... the....a....college Facebook ..definitely they will be thinking the lecturer is playing in the phone... right , so all that are stress for me, when I go back to my room and then my clique are asking me...

Other respondent also encounter similar issue which affects their confidence level. Here is comment from Respondent # 2

... because of this we aspect., we hope we can work well in the class but however we cannot do whatever they expect from us, because we put 100 % effort, we do some research, we do proper preparation before going to classbut however they do the same thing...,they put something that look weird in the Facebook. They say something bad about me..., but I got a spy that says..., yeah..., they say that i am not good in teaching....

With the development of social media, faculty is subject to lot of bullying from student which creates unpleasant working environment. The internal stress of coping with being a victim of cyber bullying can cause health issues, psychological problems, and thoughts of suicide (Juvonen & Gross, 2008; Gradinger, Strohmeier, & Sipel, 2009).

Theme 4: Unfair performance measurement

In a university, decision-making can influence whether the needs of its faculty are met or not and they will often want to make sure that the outcomes, procedures, information and people who make those decisions are doing so in the interest of faculty. As fairness in organizational decision-making processes, is an important determinant of employee cooperative attitudes and behaviors in the workplace (Cohen-Charash & Spector, 2001; Colquitt et al., 2001).

Their interests include economic and socio-emotional interest. For example, everyone needs resources to perform or fulfill the responsibilities assigned to one's role. Performance will then become an important factor for one's reward and career development in the institution. As such allocation of task or responsibility to respective

faculty must be relevant to their career development otherwise it will create unhappiness and dissatisfaction towards the institution. Here is the comment by respondent # 1

... totally disagree with that because... abhh... if a lecturer, maybe if they put in the publication every year..., let say you must have at least 2 publication, that helps the lecturer right..., but let's say marketing, what advantage did the lecturer getting,.... it only helps the university, ... they said if it helps university, it helps lecturer, so when they put that kind of KPI on lecturer's performance, I feel it's not fair.

As we see can from the above statement allocation of task which is not relevant with their main responsibility and it is being considered in their performance measurement, it creates lot of unhappiness and feel of injustice. When employees perceive organizational procedures are fair they form more positive attitudes towards the organization (Cropanzano, Prehar & Chen, 2002).

Theme 5: Unfair compensation

It is not difficult to understand why faculty concern about their fair treatment in a university. Some decisions are related to how money or other types of compensation benefits are allocated. The consequences have direct or indirect impacts on the well-being of organizational members. As Adams (1965) explained, individuals tend to look at the fairness of rewards they receive in terms of ratios. When looking at themselves, they expect rewards received to be proportional to the effort they put in to achieving those rewards.

Therefore, it is not surprising that people pay close attention to justice or fairness of rewarding, in any institution. The compensation received must be proportional to the effort they put in to achieving those rewards. Here is comment by respondent # 3

... Getting excellent for the last three years, but when I found that when it comes to promotion and increments... that was not done in away..., Systematic way or professional manner, so that make me to think, whether I am in right place..., whether I should move on or not.

It is further stated by another respondent and here is the comment by respondent # 4,

... how is the reward determined, that is also another very subjective thing, to be honest, like I said, even when I left at that time, still no clear guidelines, let say as an example, what determine the quantum of the bonus and increment, there is also, no black and white,

The above statement further clarifies that rewarding system must be transparent and the management of the institution may make an effort to explain how the system works, and what are the criteria need to fulfill and how the rewarding is being done to faculty.

Theme 6: Work overload

In working environment allocation of workload beyond the job scope of the faculty affects their morale and indirectly influences their decision to quit the position. Workload is the entire make-up of the work a person experiences or it would be the culmination of the day's work including organizational, environmental and personal workload may be categorized into skill-, rule-, and Knowledge- (SRK) based behaviors (Rasmussen, 1983).

Moreover faculty needs time to do research and publication as to enhance their knowledge and keep abreast with latest development of their related field. Here is comment by respondent # 2.

... will be quiet a burden for lectures to take all the subjects, because there will be many teaching hours will increase..., and the reason of that, also quite affecting me, because i cannot do my other work...

Another respondent also quoted a similar statement and here is the comment by respondent # 5.

... work load is heavy, because sometime you don't mind heavy workload, in terms of teaching, you don't mind, because anyway that is your specialization, teaching, the work is more on administration, paper work..., and sometime you find that this work, to be done by secretary, those who has secretary qualification, and they expecting you to demonstrate secretarial qualification...

It clearly shows that having heavy workload for faculty especially work that is not relevant with teaching job like marketing, administrative work, creates unhappiness and dissatisfaction among faculty, hence lead to quitting.

Theme 7: Job insecurity

The faculty's job status does impact their commitment and understanding towards the institution as they may feel insecure. As quoted by Cheng and Chan (2008) in his meta-analysis that showed job insecurity is related to lack of trust in management, poor loyalty, low organizational commitment, high turnover intention and lead to poor performance. This indirectly influences the faculty to look for alternative job where the other job may provide sense of security. Here is comment by respondent # 2.

... they said they will put me as a permanent staff but unfortunately.... ok I performed well , according to KPI..., mean that all the work i have been done successfully..., but the thing is that they keep continuing my contract....

The feeling of security is very important as all of us have commitment and family to look after, as such any insecurity can create lot of uneasiness and lack of confident towards the institution.

5. Conclusions

The purpose of this qualitative phenomenological study was to explore and understand the reason on why the faculty resigned from their job at private university.

Our results show that there are seven main themes emerged from this qualitative inquiry; employee image, availability of external job opportunities, social media bullying, unfairness of performance measurement, unfairness of compensation, work over load and job insecurity.

Although six themes seem to be consistent with previous theories and empirical studies on turnover, this study found an emerging new theme of social media bullying. With the development of internet technology, faculty are subject to bullying from student through social media, as such the university administrator must put in place a very clear policy regarding the usage of social media and protecting of the affected ones. This will help the faculty to seek for justice and reduce ill feeling towards the university if they are bullied. Bullying is considered a serious social problem that requires attention (Limber & Small, 2003) and it can have a long term impact on an individual's self-esteem and overall sense of well-being (O'Moore & Kirkham, 2001; Rigby, 2000).

The results of this qualitative, phenomenological study may assist educational institution administrator to see a possible need to change their institution's management. The management of the universities needs to pay attention to the image of the university as this will enhance the recruitment and maintaining their faculty and also must have clear policy on usage of social media as this will help to address bullying issue.

The study also provides university management with information about what influences faculty's resignation. The emergent themes indicate employee's dissatisfaction with the performance review, rewarding, workload and job insecurity. The management needs to

pay attention to this issue in order to improve their faculty's understanding and satisfaction.

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